

D5.4: R-Map Policy Briefs – First Version (M15)

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PROJECT OVERVIEW	R-Map aims to analyse the impact of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on the disparities between urban and rural regions in Europe. An Integrated Impact Assessment Framework (powered by the R-Map model) will be produced to assess the individual, social, economic, environmental and spatial impacts of RWAs. It will also allow decision-makers to monitor and assess how remote work arrangements affect people, communities, space, economy, and environment in urban and rural regions. Furthermore, R-Map will formulate policy recommendations on how to create environments conducive to remote work that are tailored to the needs of local governments in both urban and rural settings.

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. INTRODUCTION	10
2. EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS	10
3. SYNERGIES WITH OTHER EU-FUNDED PROJECTS & INITIATIVES	12
4. POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	12
5. SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY	16
6. RESEARCH PARAMETERS	16
7. PROJECT IDENTITY	17

List of Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
CBDs	Central Business Districts
EU	European Union
NWSs	New Working Spaces
RWAs	Remote Working Arrangements
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

Executive Summary

The rapid increase in remote work across Europe, triggered by the pandemic, has changed the way people live and work. Although this shift has continued beyond the immediate crisis, the broader implications, particularly regarding spatial, economic, and social dynamics between urban and rural areas, remain under-explored. Significant gaps exist in research and policy surrounding the potential future evolution of economic, social and spatial phenomena triggered by remote working, and their short-, medium- and long-term impact on urban-rural relationships.

The **R-Map project**, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme, aims to address this issue by mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the impact of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on urban and rural areas to inform evidence-based policy decisions. During the **first 15 months** of the project, the focus has been on gaining a deeper understanding of remote working trends and requirements.

Key insights into the spatial, economic and social impacts of remote working in urban, peri-urban and rural areas across Europe have been gathered through extensive **literature reviews**, **in-depth interviews** with policymakers, workers, employers, urban planners, regional authorities, real estate professionals and coworking space founders, a pan-European **survey of over 20,000 people**, **stakeholder engagement**, and the development of **data-driven tools**. Furthermore, R-Map has established **synergies** with several other **EU-funded projects and relevant initiatives**, including the sister projects REMAKING and WinWin4WorkLife.

The key issues identified during the first 15 months of the project that require policy intervention include differences between urban and rural areas, differences between the primary and secondary sectors, changing mobility patterns, shifting housing demand, and affordability challenges and inequalities across sectors.

In accordance with the analysis conducted during the first 15 months of the project, the following general policy recommendations are put forward:

-Development of comprehensive remote working policies: These policies should cover working hours, compensation, data management, security, privacy, and performance metrics.

-Incentivising investment in digital infrastructure: To ensure equitable access to and participation in the remote working economy, policymakers, especially at a national level, should incentivise investment in high-speed internet and digital infrastructure, particularly in rural and underserved areas.

-Supporting work-life balance and mental health: Policies should promote work-life balance and mental health by encouraging short breaks, flexible working hours and access to mental health resources.

-Promoting gender equality and diversity: Remote working can enhance gender equality and diversity. Policies should encourage inclusive practices that support women and underrepresented groups in remote settings. This ensures equal access to opportunities, addresses the gender pay gap, and supports caregivers and parents.

Based on the above, the key initial policy recommendations for the **first reporting period (M1-M15)** could be specified as follows:

Short-term (immediate actions):

- ❖ Establish metropolitan and local observatories to monitor remote working trends and provide data-driven recommendations.
- ❖ Implement fiscal compensation mechanisms for public transport facing reduced revenues.
- ❖ Reform zoning laws to encourage the creation of mixed-use districts for flexible workspaces.

Medium-term (strategic investments):

- ❖ Increase investment in digital infrastructure to support remote working.
- ❖ Strengthen metropolitan planning frameworks to coordinate economic development.
- ❖ Develop workforce adaptation programmes to retrain workers in displaced sectors.

Long-term (policy integration):

- ❖ Incorporate RWAs into national and EU policies.
- ❖ Develop sustainable strategies that balance urban and regional economic growth.
- ❖ Promote resilience by incorporating work flexibility into national employment policies.

These recommendations are primarily intended for policymakers at the local, metropolitan/regional, national and EU levels, as well as for heads of policy in private and public companies, urban planning practitioners at local, regional and national levels, as well as private companies and investors.

In conclusion, this document summarises the key findings from the first 15 months of the R-Map project, along with the initial policy recommendations derived from these findings. The document **will be updated at the end of the project (M36)**.

1. Introduction

This document constitutes the **first version of D5.4: R-Map Policy Briefs**, which explores the possible contents of the final version (M36) based on the project R-Map's mid-term outcomes (M15). The project, '*R-Map: Mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of RWAs in urban and rural areas*', is funded by the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, under Grant Agreement No. 101132497.

The aim of R-Map is to analyse the impact of RWAs on urban and rural settings, and how it influences the urban-rural divide in Europe. R-Map will develop an integrated impact assessment framework using the R-Map model to assess the individual, social, economic, environmental and spatial impacts of remote work. A visualisation platform will be created to enable decisionmakers to monitor and evaluate how remote work affects people, communities, space, the economy and the environment in urban and rural areas. The tools will be applied at the local level in six representative use cases in the European Union (EU) and the Associated Countries (AC), including regions in Greece, the UK, Italy, Türkiye, the Netherlands-Germany and Austria-Switzerland. Using scenario building and forecasting methods, R-Map will explore the potential future impact of remote work in these regions over the next 5-10 years and provide policy recommendations for national, regional, or local governments in both urban and rural areas, that intend to provide those with the broadest and clearer information to access sustained decision making in all fields.

2. Evidence and analysis

Over the past 15 months, the R-Map project has focused on improving our understanding of remote working trends and needs. Through extensive literature reviews, in-depth interviews, stakeholder engagement and the creation of data-driven tools, key insights have been gained into the spatial, economic and social impacts of remote working in urban, peri-urban and rural areas across Europe.

These include:

Exploring the current landscape of remote work: An extensive literature review and 15 interviews with policymakers, workers, employers and trade union members on RWAs, in Europe and beyond, were conducted to identify key enablers and barriers. The findings highlight how technological advances have facilitated hybrid and fully remote work models, while differences in digital infrastructure, socio-economic conditions, and policy frameworks still pose significant challenges, particularly in rural areas. Before considering the role of remote work in shaping local economies or the global labor market, the different configurations of remote work should be better understood and fully addressed by policymakers. Different countries use different definitions and approaches to remote work and, in some cases, remote work can be understood as a job role, in others as a working arrangement.

Investigation of the spatial implications of RWAs in Europe and beyond: 21 in-depth interviews were conducted across eight locations in Europe and the US, engaging urban planners, regional authorities, real estate professionals, coworking space founders, and more. The research highlighted that remote work is associated with the emergence of new working spaces (NWSs) such as coworking spaces, shared office hubs and other hybrid models. The emergence of these new spatialities of work reflects changing preferences for flexible work

locations that blur the boundaries between home, work and community life. Key findings underline the significant changes in urban development trends, with a marked decline in central business districts (CBDs) in favor of suburban growth and the rise of small and medium-sized cities in rural and remote areas. This trend reflects a wider shift in housing preferences towards spacious, affordable living environments. Demand for office space has also shifted accordingly, affecting both urban regeneration and rural development. Mobility patterns have also changed significantly, with reduced commuting leading to changes in demand for transport infrastructure. However, these trends also pose significant challenges, such as excessive land consumption, gentrification, and strain on local infrastructure.

Assessing the socio-economic implications of RWAs: A global literature review and 31 stakeholder interviews were conducted to understand the wider economic and social impacts of remote work. The results suggest that a number of organizations are already quite advanced in their use of remote work in the workplace. At the same time, differences have emerged between the public and private sectors, and between larger employers and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Although different groups of employees face different challenges, it is interesting to note that remote work appears to have shifted certain types of costs to employees, either consciously or unconsciously. At the same time, emerging trends such as digital nomads are still not fully explored or understood, which have been observed to pose challenges in terms of taxation or social security. Such challenges are exacerbated in cross-border situations.

Conducting a large-scale survey: 20,013 Europeans shared their perceptions of remote work, including its challenges, benefits and needs. Findings highlight that benefits are a key driver, with a significant preference for remote work among participants. Commute times average roughly half an hour, with a considerable share using private vehicles and a smaller portion relying on public transport. At the same time, it seems that remote work preferences are linked to lower perceived career impact, which may indicate that those who choose remote work do not feel it hinders their career that much. Based on the results of this survey, two papers are planned to be published.

Co-designing the R-Map model: Through extensive discussions, partners, experts and AB members collaborated to lay the foundations for co-creating the conceptual model, which serves as a framework for assessing the spatial, economic & social impacts of remote work. 3 other technical workshops and 1 validation workshop were conducted online. The latter involved AB members and members of sister projects, who provided valuable input to refine the conceptual model. Finally, the model has been implemented as an operational Bayesian Network in Python programming language. It is an open-source platform that can be deployed as a standalone application to model and understand the impacts of remote working.

Developing the architecture of the R-Map platform: Extensive desk research was conducted to identify & define the specifications of recognised and widely accepted visualisation tools. In addition, an online technical workshop was organised with partners to discuss the platform's user requirements, and an online validation workshop was held with Advisory Board (AB) members to review the suggested user interface/user experience of the platform. The architecture of the R-Map platform has been finalised through this process. The first version of the platform is set to launch by M20.

3. Synergies with other EU-funded projects & initiatives

The project actively seeks synergies with relevant EU-funded projects and other relevant initiatives to maximise impact. Up until M15, R-Map has established synergies with 9 projects, initiatives and networks. Among these, R-Map established synergies with the two sister projects funded under the same call ([REMAKING & WinWin4WorkLife](#)), with which it also created a “Sister Project Collaboration Framework” depicting areas of potential collaboration among the three projects. Collaborating with relevant projects and initiatives allows for knowledge exchange and enhances the uptake of results by a broader range of stakeholders. These strategic partnerships contribute to more coherent, coordinated and relevant results at the EU level and act as multipliers, extending the project’s outreach.

4. Policy implications and recommendations

The increase of remote work is reshaping urban dynamics, particularly in metropolitan regions. After all, it is at this territorial level that this transformation is influencing mobility patterns, housing demand, the real estate markets, and labour market structures, necessitating a strategic response from policymakers at multiple levels of governance. Local authorities, metropolitan institutions, and national governments must collaborate to facilitate a smooth transition that promotes economic resilience, spatial equity, and social inclusivity. Effective adaptation to remote work requires policies that address both immediate disruptions and long-term structural changes. This first policy brief reviews and takes stock of the results of the first 15 months of the project, examines the key challenges posed by remote work and aims to explore the field of a comprehensive set of recommendations to ensure regional and metropolitan regions can adapt to these shifts in an equitable and sustainable manner. The objective is to communicate these results to policymakers in an easily understandable and accessible way, with a special focus on the European context.

1. Key Issues

Urban / rural and primary / secondary sector differences

The main economic sector(s) in each region has(have) a major influence on the availability or prevalence of remote work. The strategic approach should not consider only numbers related to remote work but also the reality of the social and economic fabrics. In fact, remote work might be an opportunity to balance territorial inequalities in and improve economic dynamics spread over Metropolitan regions and areas between the urban settings and the more rural areas. The urban planning approach to the metropolis and the larger city — with strict zoning areas and specific functions—which might have been the main factor in shaping the city and society as a whole in recent decades, surely will be influenced by the outcomes of this analysis and can draw on the results of the foreseen visualization platform. New approaches in spatial planning, its policies and instruments, are necessary, as it is to raise awareness amidst involved professionals and politicians.

Changing Mobility Patterns

Although varying across regions, remote work has overall significantly reduced daily commuting, leading to a decline in the demand for traditional public transportation services. This shift calls for a review of urban

mobility policies to balance the evolving needs of commuters, still ensuring a financial sustainability of transport infrastructure. Additionally, there has been a marked increase in localised mobility within residential areas, as more individuals engage in remote work from home or coworking spaces in suburban and peri urban locations. Policymakers will have to address the financial implications of reduced transport revenues while also investing in alternative mobility solutions, which could be the likes of micro-mobility services, flexible public transport schedules, and pedestrian-friendly urban planning.

Shifting Housing Demand and Affordability Challenges

The widespread adoption of remote work has led to a reconfiguration of housing preferences, with increasing demand for larger living spaces, primarily located in suburban and rural areas. This trend has contributed to rising property prices in these regions, exacerbating affordability challenges for low- and middle-income households. In contrast, urban centres are witnessing shifts in commercial real estate demand, with declining occupancy rates in central business districts. Addressing these changes requires adaptive housing policies, including zoning reforms to support mixed-use developments, incentives for affordable housing projects, and regulatory adjustments to accommodate flexible live-work arrangements that provide the necessary space and conditions. All of this comes on top of an already overheated and changing real estate market. With growing limitations on new land take, including a survey on the existing building stock should be taken into consideration as well. Integration of RWAs related policies within metropolitan or regional housing policies, possibly with a new EU Agenda for Housing is recommended.

Inequalities across Sectors, Territories, and Income Groups

The benefits of remote work are not uniformly distributed across the labour market, with possibly widening socio-economic disparities. High-income professionals in knowledge-based industries have greater access to remote work opportunities, whereas employees in service, manufacturing, and essential sectors face ongoing constraints in accessing such arrangements. Moreover, territorial inequalities are emerging, as economically vibrant metropolitan regions attract remote workers, while less developed areas struggle with depopulation and economic stagnation. To mitigate these disparities, policy interventions must focus on expanding remote work opportunities for diverse economic sectors, supporting digital infrastructure in underserved areas, and fostering regional economic diversification.

2. Recommendations

The research and analysis conducted so far (from WP1) has provided the foundation for some general policy recommendations.

- Development of Comprehensive Remote Work Policies

Governments and organisations should establish clear and comprehensive remote work policies that address the specific needs and challenges of remote work. These policies should cover socio- economic issues such as working hours, compensation, data management and security, privacy and performance metrics. A well-defined policy framework can help mitigate potential legal and employment challenges, fostering a supportive environment for remote workers and their employers. This would be beneficial in both the short and long term, allowing organisations to be more agile and adaptive.

- Incentivising Investment in Digital Infrastructure

To enhance the productivity and efficiency of remote work, policymakers, mainly on the national level, should incentivise investment in high-speed internet and digital infrastructure, especially in rural and underserved areas. Improved access to reliable and affordable internet will ensure that all employees, regardless of their location, can participate fully in the remote work economy. Concurrently, relevant training and support should be provided to all stakeholders ranging from remote workers, their managers, health services, tax authorities, Destination Management Organisations, local authorities.

- Supporting Work-Life Balance and Mental Health

Remote work can blur the boundaries between work and personal life, leading to increased stress and burnout. Policies should be developed to support employees' work-life balance and mental health, such as short breaks, flexible working hours, and access to mental health resources. Employers should also be encouraged to offer training and support programmes that help employees manage remote work's unique challenges. Such measures are essential for ensuring the long-term well-being and productivity of remote workers.

- Promoting Gender Equality and Diversity in Remote Work

Remote work offers the potential to enhance gender equality and diversity in the workplace by providing flexible working arrangements that can accommodate diverse needs. Policies should encourage employers to adopt inclusive practices that support women and underrepresented groups in remote work settings. This includes ensuring equal access to opportunities, addressing the gender pay gap, and creating a supportive environment for caregivers and parents.

The key initial policy recommendations for the first reporting period (M1-M15) could be specified as follows:

Short-term (Immediate Actions)

- Establish metropolitan and local observatories to systematically monitor remote work trends, assess economic and social impacts, and provide data-driven policy recommendations. This could be a national initiative, but it should be implemented by metropolitan and regional authorities to ensure a thorough understanding of local circumstances.
- Implement fiscal compensation mechanisms to support public transport systems facing declining revenues due to reduced commuter flows. This can only be initiated by the national government and implemented by metropolitan/regional and local authorities.
- Reform zoning laws to encourage the development of mixed-use districts that integrate residential, commercial, and services, allowing flexible workspaces, thus creating a dynamic to accommodate changing work patterns. This can be initiated and implemented by metropolitan/regional and local authorities in land-use plans.

Medium-term (Strategic Investments)

- Expand investment in digital infrastructure to support RWAs, ensuring equitable access to high-speed internet and reliable mobility options across all regions. The negotiations for these investments should include national, metropolitan/regional and private business representatives.

- Strengthen metropolitan planning frameworks to coordinate economic development strategies that balance the growth of urban, suburban, and rural areas. This is the competence of metropolitan/regional and local authorities.
- Develop workforce adaptation programmes that provide retraining opportunities for workers in sectors experiencing displacement due to shifts in workplace demands. This is a very broad action to which public authorities, business sector, employees' representatives and educational institutions should participate.

Long-term (Policy Integration)

- Institutionalize RWAs into national and European Union policies, ensuring that long-term labour market regulations align with evolving work arrangements. This is primarily a task for national and EU policy makers, including representations of the business sector and labour markets. Educational institutions can play a supportive role.
- Develop sustainable strategies to balance urban and regional economic growth. This is primarily a coordination task by the metropolitan/regional and local authorities, using broad consultation processes including all stakeholders.
- Promote resilience by embedding work flexibility into national employment policies, ensuring that future economic shocks can be mitigated through adaptive labour market structures. This is a national and EU competence.

3. The intended audience for the above recommendations is mainly:

- Policymakers at the local, metropolitan/regional, national and EU levels.
- Heads responsible for policies in private and public companies or institutions.
- Urban planning practitioners at local, regional and national levels.
- Private companies and investors, and possibly educational institutions.

4. Expected Impact

- *Resilient and Balanced Metropolitan Regions:* By implementing adaptive policies, metropolitan areas will be better equipped to navigate the economic and social challenges posed by remote work, ensuring sustainable urban development.
- *Improved Housing Affordability and Mobility:* A strategic approach to housing and transport planning can help mitigate affordability crises, enhance accessibility, and support equitable urban transformation while providing social balance.
- *Reduced Spatial Inequalities:* Targeted interventions will address disparities between income groups, economic sectors, and geographical areas, fostering a more inclusive and diversified economic landscape.

By adopting these recommendations, metropolitan regions can proactively shape the future of work and living, ensuring that remote work serves as a driver of sustainable economic development and social well-being rather than a source of inequality and disruption.

5. Sustainability and legacy

The main legacy of the project will be the R-Map visualisation platform, which will provide researchers and policymakers with a comprehensive and interactive tool for exploring data on RWAs. The platform will integrate the R-Map model, an assessment framework of the social, economic, and spatial impacts of the RWAs, as a background algorithm and additional datasets to provide an operational tool to visualise the assessment of the individual, socio-economic and spatial impacts of RWAs and to simulate adaptive what-if scenarios. In addition, the project will release a regional typology & taxonomy of RWAs to classify EU regions based on a specific set of characteristics related to the different dimensions of the urban-rural divide, enriched by a taxonomy of socio-economic factors.

6. Research parameters

The overall aim of the R-Map project is to explore how remote work affects the urban-rural gap in Europe by mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of RWAs. To this end, an integrated impact assessment framework (the R-Map model) will be created and an internet platform using this model will be developed to provide visualisation and interactive services.

The consortium members have carried out extensive literature reviews, in-depth interviews with various stakeholders and experts (including policymakers, employees, employers, union members, urban planners, real estate professionals, coworking space founders, and more), an online survey with over 20,000 participants and a physical co-creation workshop to validate the findings of the desk research and to co-design the R-Map model. All this has led to the development of several reports on the context of RWAs and their spatial, economic and social impacts (Deliverables 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4). In addition, the R-Map consortium, with the help of AB members, domain experts, and others, has co-created the R-Map conceptual model, which serves as a framework for assessing the impacts of remote work (Deliverable 2.1). At the same time, the architecture of the R-Map platform (Deliverable 3.1) has been completed, and its development is underway.

7. Project identity

PROJECT NAME	Mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of remote working arrangements in urban and rural areas (R-Map)
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